

Quantification of CO and Further CO₂ Reduction Products by On-line Mass Spectrometry

Jonas Englhard^[a] and Julien Bachmann^{*[a]}

The reduction of CO₂ in water can yield a variety of volatile products mixed with the starting material and often dinitrogen as an inert gas. While mass spectrometry is ideally suited to the quantitative analysis of gases in low concentrations, the simultaneous detection is usually performed with a preliminary chromatographic separation. In its absence, the mass spectrometric signal at $m/z=28$ can be due to CO, CO₂, and N₂. Here, we demonstrate that ionizing the mixture of reaction products

under 16 eV results in the selective detection of CO at $m/z=28$, at the complete exclusion of CO₂ and N₂. This method is applicable to headspace analysis after a bulk electrolysis and delivers product compositions as they depend on catalyst and applied potential. Furthermore, its immediate nature also enables the experimentalist to perform, in real time, a direct monitoring of the reaction products generated during cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

Containing the rise in carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels in the atmosphere can be achieved in two complementary ways, either the plain reduction in emissions, or the conversion of CO₂ back into chemical feedstocks in order to accomplish a carbon cycle.^[1] The electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR) enables the conversion of CO₂ into carbon monoxide (CO), formic acid, ethylene, methane, and even more complex multi-carbon products, depending on the electrolysis conditions and the nature of electrocatalyst used.^[2] The CO₂RR to CO is especially promising due to the relative mechanistic simplicity of the reaction and the existing demand for CO in syngas generation or in several industrial processes such as the Monsanto acetic acid or Fischer-Tropsch processes.^[1b,3] Among the conceivable CO₂ conversion pathways, the CO₂-to-CO reduction is therefore closest to being operated at industrial scale.^[1c,4] High selectivity towards CO generation is found for working electrodes composed of Au, Ag, Zn or Pd, as these metals feature a low binding energy towards the adsorbed CO formed as an intermediate on the electrode's surface.^[2c,5]

To find the best electrocatalysts and to optimize CO₂RR conditions in terms of selectivity, it is crucial to identify and quantify both liquid and gaseous reaction products. Liquid CO₂RR products are usually quantified by NMR or by liquid

chromatographic separation coupled to various detectors.^[6] The common way of analyzing the gaseous electroreduction products is gas chromatographic separation of analytes, followed by their individual detection by flame ionization or thermal conductivity detectors or by mass spectrometry.^[2a,6] While this method provides reproducible quantitative results, it does have some drawbacks such as the need for regular calibrations to yield accurate results.^[7] Furthermore, if the time-dependent evolution of gases is subject of investigation, due to the chromatographic nature of the method only allowing for intermittent sampling, it is required to carry out multiple time-consuming measurements, limiting the overall response time and impeding the gathering of time-dependent information on product formation.^[8]

Another, more time-sensitive method to investigate product generation is on-line mass spectrometric analysis of the products formed.^[2a,b,9] The key requirement for this method to reproducibly work is the ability to identify the individual analytes by unique ions generated upon ionization. Several studies have stated that CO is not quantifiable as a CO₂RR product via direct on-line mass spectrometry analysis due to its molecular ion's overlap with the fragmentation spectrum of carbon dioxide, which is present in excess concentration as the starting material.^[2b,10] In the present study, we demonstrate that CO can be detected with absolute specificity at the exclusion of CO₂ and N₂ present in excess. The key to this success is the adequate adjustment of ionization conditions to avoid CO₂ fragmentation. While the effect of ionization potential on fragmentation is well documented and has been exploited to diminish interferences,^[8,11] the direct detection of the CO product signal in the presence of CO₂ has not been demonstrated with total elimination of the CO₂ contribution. Therefore, CO detection has so far only been possible in cases in which the product concentration is large – otherwise, subtraction of the CO₂ contribution to the signal at $m/z=28$ renders the quantification questionable. In the following, we will present the methods allowing for this direct, selective, zero-background quantification of CO and we apply it to headspace gas analysis

[a] J. Englhard, Prof. J. Bachmann
Chemistry of Thin Film Materials
Department of Chemistry and Pharmacy
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg
IZNF, Cauerstr. 3
91058 Erlangen, Germany
E-mail: julien.bachmann@fau.de

Supporting information for this article is available on the WWW under <https://doi.org/10.1002/cmtd.202300019>

© 2023 The Authors. Chemistry - Methods published by Chemistry Europe and Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

as well as to dynamic CO₂RR experiments (differential electrochemical mass spectrometry, DEMS) in which the composition of products is analyzed in real time as it depends on the electrocatalyst nature and the applied potential.

Results and Discussion

Quantification of CO in a gas mixture by low-energy ionization MS

In all CO₂RR experiments, regardless of the electrochemical cell design, CO₂ is always present in the mixture to be analyzed, often in a large excess. Therefore, a key requirement is to be able to distinguish between CO₂ and the product gas CO in any mass spectrometric analysis. In the mass spectrum of pure CO₂, the ratio of the molecular ion peak CO₂⁺ at $m/z=44$ to the fragment peak CO⁺ at $m/z=28$ is a value that is either known from the literature or that can easily be determined instrument-specifically by sampling pure CO₂.^[11b,12] Therefore, after so-called matrix correction by measuring the CO₂ concentration at $m/z=44$, in theory any surplus in intensity found experimentally at $m/z=28$ can be attributed to the presence of CO.^[13] However, this method is only valid for reasonably high levels of CO present in the analyte mixture. If the CO content produced during the CO₂RR is in the low percent range or lower, its low signal-to-noise level will render the quantification impossible or questionable at best.^[2b,14] Therefore, a method is required to avoid the fragmentation of CO₂⁺.

This can be achieved by deviating from the standard ionization conditions used in electron impact mass spectrometry. A kinetic energy of 70 eV is used mostly based on optimized ionization yields. Here, we will employ a reduced ionization energy in order to render the process chemically selective by lowering the voltage applied to the filament that serves as the electron source.^[11b] Figure 1 shows the yields (as partial pressures) obtained upon sampling pure CO₂ for the molecular ion (apart from C¹⁸O¹⁶O⁺) and of all possible singly charged fragmentation products as they depend on the ionization energy E_i .

With increasing ionization energy, CO₂ starts to ionize to its molecular ion CO₂⁺ at $m/z=44$ (including the 1% ¹³CO₂⁺ at $m/z=45$) at energies larger than about 15 eV. Starting at approximately 20 eV, fragmentation of CO₂⁺ sets in, and CO⁺ and O⁺ are detected in equal amounts. Finally, at about 32 eV, enough energy is provided to cleave both bonds of CO₂ to yield C⁺ fragments. This fragmentation behavior of CO₂ indicates for our purpose that for ionization energies smaller than 20 eV, no fragmentation of CO₂⁺ will interfere with measurements of CO product gas levels.

Let us now consider the ionization behavior of the various gases of interest in the onset region between 15 and 20 eV. Figure 2 shows that the ionization of CO₂ (green) and CO (purple) to their respective molecular ions require a minimum of 15 eV approximately and that from there on, the signal intensities increase linearly with increasing ionization energy (in the investigated region). N₂, the molecular ion of which also

Figure 1. Signal intensities observed for selected ions at various ionization energies when sampling 100% CO₂: molecular ion signals are shown in green, the fragmentation products C⁺, O⁺ and CO⁺ are displayed in blue, orange and pink, respectively. Ionization of CO₂ to its molecular ion starts at around 15 eV. Fragmentation of CO₂ starts at around 20 eV. Below 20 eV, no significant amounts of fragment ions are obtained.

Figure 2. Molecular ion yields obtained in the onset region for ionization of different pure gases. Partial pressures of the molecular ions of nitrogen, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide are displayed vs. ionization energy in blue, purple, and green, respectively.

appears at $m/z=28$, starts to ionize at higher energies of 17 eV. Hereby, N₂⁺ and CO⁺ exhibit very similar slopes of the partial pressure curves, whereas the slope obtained for CO₂⁺ is significantly larger. This is expected and in agreement with sensitivity factors used in residual gas analysis (RGA), corresponding to the different analyte-specific ionization cross-sections.^[15]

These preliminary measurements allow us to identify 16 eV as an ionization energy at which CO can be quantified at the exclusion of interferences caused by N₂ and by CO₂ fragmentation products. Figure 3 establishes that this is the case by presenting the calibration curve determined at $m/z=28$ upon varying the CO/N₂/CO₂ mixtures (whereby CO₂ is

Figure 3. Partial pressures of two selected ions with $m/z=28$ and $m/z=44$ (corresponding to N_2 or CO and to CO_2 , respectively) determined for various CO/N_2 concentration ratios in the presence of a constant excess (50%) of CO_2 . The results obtained at the ionization energy chosen for the remainder of this study, $E_i=16$ eV (lower half), are compared with those at a less appropriate value of 19 eV (top half of the figure). At both E_i values, the signal for $m/z=28$ increases linearly with increasing fractions of CO , the signal for $m/z=44$ stays constant in both measurements as expected. However, the $m/z=28$ signal is zero for 0% CO only at $E_i=16$ eV.

always present as the major component at constant 50%, pink datapoints). Crucially, the calibration curve crosses the origin: At $E_i=16$ eV, no signal appears when no CO is present, despite the overwhelming presence of N_2 and CO_2 , both of which are therefore completely eliminated as interferences. This contrasts the situation obtained at $E_i=19$ eV, where linearity is given as well but with a non-zero signal at 0% CO (purple curve). In both cases, the signal at $m/z=44$ associated with CO_2 is constant.

Of course, ionizing at $E_i=16$ eV instead of the standard value of 70 eV reduces the ion yield and the overall sensitivity accordingly. However, this can be readily compensated by using secondary electron multiplier detectors to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio. We further propose that for studies of electroreduction of isotopically labelled $^{13}CO_2$, a higher ionization energy of $E_i=19$ eV could be used in order to further increase ionization cross-sections and therefore enhance the $^{13}CO^+$ signal at $m/z=29$ over noise. This ionization energy is still below the threshold required to fragment $^{13}CO_2$ and the low abundance of $^{15}N^{14}N$ would further suppress the background signal at $m/z=29$ to negligible values.

We also note that while the $E_i=16$ eV parameter enables the experimentalist to distinguish CO from CO_2 and N_2 , ethylene C_2H_4 remains as a potential contaminant. This is relevant to electrochemical CO_2RR research as ethylene belongs to the range of possible reduction products.^[16] However, ethylene is never present in overwhelming concentration in this application and it can be identified, quantified and accounted for by its fragmentation peak at $m/z=27$.

Application: CO_2RR mixed product analysis by MS

Let us now demonstrate the viability of the method described for quantifying CO in real applications by analyzing the product gas mixtures obtained upon electrochemical CO_2RR on various metals. The experiment is carried out in a closed three-electrode electrochemical cell containing 20.0 mL of a pH-neutral, CO_2 -sparged 0.5 M $KHCO_3$ electrolyte solution with 3.5 mL headspace. Electrolyses are performed at different applied potentials, namely -1.2 V, -1.0 V and -0.8 V versus RHE, under chronocoulometric monitoring until 10 C have passed. At this point, the headspace gas composition is sampled with a microflow inlet and analyzed towards its CO content (with a calibration procedure described in the Supporting Information) using $E_i=16$ eV, whereas all other product gases (H_2 , CH_4 and C_2H_4) can be quantified using standard RGA-MS parameters (including $E_i=70$ eV).

The results presented in Figure 4 establish our procedure as a dependable and sensitive analysis technique for fast MS quantification of CO in a CO_2RR gas mixture. Comparing the four different metal catalysts shows the contrasting selectivities known from the literature: Pt generates almost exclusively H_2 ,^[17] Ag and Au are most efficient towards CO ,^[18] Cu is the only one of the four metals enabling further reduction to lower oxidation states of C.^[2b,14,19] Clear trends are also obtained when for a given metal the overpotential is varied, with both overall yield and product composition affected. The experiments on Au repeated five times enable us to draw error bars (Figure 4a) which demonstrate the validity of the experimental values. Importantly, the overall CO concentrations are mostly in the

Figure 4. Fractions of selected CO_2RR product gases present in the headspace of a sealed electrochemical cell after electrolysis. Carbon monoxide, hydrogen, methane, and ethylene are displayed in grey, red, blue and green, respectively. In every experiment, a single-compartment three-electrode setup with a leakless AgCl reference electrode and a platinum counter-electrode was used. Gold (a), silver (b), platinum (c) or copper (d) wires were used as working electrodes to catalyze the electrochemical CO_2RR . The cell is filled with 20 mL CO_2 -saturated 0.5 M $KHCO_3$ -solution and electrolyzed at different potentials until a charge of 10 C has passed. The headspace volume is approximately 3.5 mL. The exact values can be found in Table S1 in the Supporting Information.

range of 1% and can be determined reproducibly despite the presence of CO_2 in a large excess.

Real-time CO detection during differential electrochemical MS (DEMS)

The ability to identify CO and other species in the reaction mixture selectively by MS purely (as opposed to GC-MS) enables us to apply the method to the analysis of dynamic electrochemical CO_2 RR systems in real time. To achieve this goal, the MS inlet is modified from the simple capillary (inserted into the head space) to a nanoporous membrane inlet immersed in the aqueous electrolyte. When this inlet is placed in immediate vicinity of the working electrode, the electrolytically evolved gases are injected directly into the mass spectrometer. Figure 5

Figure 5. Real-time application of direct mass spectrometric analysis of electrochemical CO_2 RR products – mass voltammograms. The voltammograms are recorded in a three-electrode setup with Au (a–d) or Ag (e) as the working electrode and in a CO_2 -saturated 0.5 MKHCO₃ as electrolyte. Potential and current density curves are shown in (c). H_2O , H_2 and CO_2 are analysed in standard ionization conditions with $E_i = 70$ eV in (a), CO is quantified at $m/z = 28$ with $E_i = 16$ eV in (b). The CO^+ -trace recorded for $m/z = 28$ at $E_i = 70$ eV in (a) demonstrates the necessity of our method, as it is not possible to distinguish between CO product and N_2/CO_2 . The subset figure aims to compare peak shapes of the H_2 and CO generated (CO detected at $E_i = 16$ eV) on Au (d) and Ag (e). The average peak-positions allow us to determine the time between product generation and detection to be $10(\pm 1)$ s.

displays exemplary traces obtained with this method for selected molecular ions vs. time, while performing cyclic voltammetry on a planar Au working electrode:

- MS analysis with standard ionization energy $E_i = 70$ eV identifies H_2O^+ as the major ion, expectedly (Figure 5a, upper blue trace). Its intensity, while not perfectly constant due to the formation and evolution of bubbles, is not correlated to the voltage signal. The intensities determined (at $E_i = 70$ eV) for H_2^+ , CO^+ and CO_2^+ are more than an order of magnitude smaller (Figure 5a).
- The H_2^+ signal draws a curve modulated along the current density trace (Figure 5c) generated as a result of the (negative) applied potential. The mostly smooth curve is perturbed by occasional peaks caused by the separation of large gas bubbles from the surface. We observe a minimal time delay between reaching the most negative potential value and detecting the maximal amount of product, corresponding to transport across the electrolyte and through the injection system.
- That the CO_2^+ curve also depends on voltage may be unexpected at first, but is logical given that a CO_2 -saturated solution will always deliver CO_2 gas into each bubble formed of another gas in order to establish an equilibrium. Therefore, it correlates with the overall throughput of the electrocatalytic reaction.
- The CO-derived signal at $E_i = 70$ eV is too low for any significant conclusions to be drawn from the purple trace shown in Figure 5a, as demonstrated in Figures 1–3 (given that the $m/z = 28$ signal is dominated by ions derived from N_2 and CO_2 present in excess concentration). Essentially the purple curve in Figure 5a ($m/z = 28$ under 70 eV) follows the green curve ($m/z = 44$ for the CO_2^+ ion) and contains no interpretable additional information. However, the CO^+ trace collected at $m/z = 28$ under the lower ionization energy of $E_i = 16$ eV allows for the specific detection of carbon monoxide. Accordingly, it exhibits a modulation of chemical yield based on applied potential analogous to H_2 (Figure 5b).

Further chemical insight is provided by comparing the exact shapes of the H_2 and CO traces recorded on Au and Ag electrodes (Figure 5d and Figure 5e, respectively; the full dataset recorded on Ag is presented in the Supporting Information, Figure S3). In order to minimize the noise caused by bubbles, the raw data must be processed by averaging over at least three CV cycles (with linear interpolation where needed). Furthermore, Voigt functions can be fitted on the experimental points to guide the eye ($R^2 > 0.97$) and scaled in order to improve ease of comparison. On Au, the fraction of CO generated is large at intermediary applied potentials, and it decreases in favor of H_2 formation at large negative potentials. The behavior on the Ag electrode is opposed to this, with a monotonic decrease of H_2 fraction with increase in the (negative) cathodic potential applied. These observations are fully in line with the less detailed dataset determined for these two metals at only three potential values in Figure 4, as well as with the relevant literature.^[8b,18b,20]

The method presented here enables the experimentalist to pinpoint precisely how the selectivity for CO evolution depends

on applied potential for each metal. A quantitative transfer of the curve from the time axis to applied potential (as the abscissa) relies on the knowledge of the delay between product generation at the electrode and analysis in the MS instrument. This delay can be derived from the curves shown in Figure 5 and is highly reproducible as long as the geometry of the electrolysis setup including MS probe is maintained. In our conditions, this value was found to be $10(\pm 1)$ s. The curves obtained (Figure S4 in the Supporting Information) allow one to choose their electrolysis conditions based on desired throughput and product composition. Specifically, the data suggest -0.8 V as a potential around which Au generates the largest fraction of CO. The data can even be further treated to generate mechanistic insight: Tafel curves converted from Figure 5d imply that the mechanism of CO evolution might change at approximately -0.9 V (Figure S4b).

Conclusions

Quantifying CO as a product of electrochemical CO₂RR is rendered possible in direct mass spectrometry analysis by low-energy electron impact ionization at $E_i=16$ eV. In these conditions, which are independent of the technical details of the spectrometer, carbon monoxide can be detected specifically, at the exclusion of both N₂⁺ and fragmentation products of CO₂, without the need to couple the mass spectrometer to any preliminarily chromatographic separation method. This technique can be employed to analyze headspace compositions of CO₂RR experiments using various catalysts and the selectivity for CO generation optimized based on experimental parameters such as the applied potential. Interference by ethylene potentially also present as a reaction product can be prevented by performing analyses at both $E_i=16$ eV and $E_i=70$ eV.

Furthermore, the immediacy of the analysis renders it applicable to real-time monitoring. For example, it enables one to plot 'mass voltammograms', that is, the direct presentation of the product composition while the potential is varied continuously at the electrode. This allows not only for fast characterization of the reactivity profiles of novel electrode materials towards the electrochemical CO₂-to-CO reduction in the future, it also generates insight into reaction mechanisms as delivered by Tafel plots in cases featuring product mixtures.

Established methods towards similar goals include GC-MS and on-line ICP-MS analysis. In the former case, the inherent timescale of chromatography limits the achievable time resolution to values on the order of several minutes. The latter method, which has been applied mostly to the quantification of corrosion phenomena, is much more immediate, but it also features a lag time on the order of several seconds and is typically performed with slow voltametric cycling on the timescale of a minute or so.^[21] Therefore, the DEMS-derived method presented here delivers a state-of-the-art time resolution.

Experimental Section

Chemicals

Chemicals are of analytical reagent grade, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, and then used as received. Pt, Au, and Ag wires of $\geq 99.9\%$ purity were purchased from Advent Research Materials. Technical-grade Cu wire was dipped in aqueous HCl solution to remove the oxide layer and used as is. The pure gases CO, CO₂, and N₂ were purchased from Linde in purities of N4.7, N3.5, and N5.0, respectively.

Carbon dioxide electrolysis

All measurements were carried out at room temperature on Gamry Interface 1000 potentiostats in a CO₂-saturated aqueous 0.5 M KHCO₃ solution (pH = 7.30). For the electrochemical measurements, a three-electrode setup featuring a Pt mesh counter electrode and a Ag/AgCl reference electrode (standard potential shifted -0.21 V compared to the standard hydrogen electrode SHE) was used. The potential was converted to vs. RHE (reversible hydrogen electrode) using the following equation [Eq. (1)]:

$$E(\text{RHE}) = E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.059 \text{ V} \times \text{pH} + 0.21 \text{ V} \quad (1)$$

The working electrode consisted of a 3 cm long wire of the respective pure metal. A gas-tight, septum-sealed single-compartment electrochemical cell was used to be able to collect and analyze the evolving gases. The cell was filled with 20.0 mL electrolyte in N₂-atmosphere and then sealed tight. Chronocoulometric measurements were performed at different applied potentials of -0.8 V, -1.0 V or -1.2 V (vs. RHE) until a charge of 10 C (in some instances 5 C, the resulting amount of gas has been doubled in this case) had passed. Subsequently, headspace gas analysis was performed.

For the DEMS measurements, planar working electrodes were used as catalysts towards the electrochemical CO₂RR. The gold electrode was prepared by DC-sputtering a 150 nm thick Au film on a Ti foil substrate (5 nm Cr adhesion layer sputtered in between) using a reactor from Torr International Inc. The silver electrode was made by thermally evaporating an 80 nm thick Ag film onto the gold Au electrodes. To define the electrochemically active area for both electrodes, a mask made from polyimide tape (Kapton®), featuring a laser-cut circular hole with a diameter of 6.0 mm, was glued on the planar electrodes. In all DEMS measurements, a three-electrode electrochemical cell filled with 60 mL of a CO₂-saturated aqueous 0.5 M HCO₃ solution was used. Four voltammetric cycles were performed from -0.4 to -1.2 V vs. RHE with a scan rate of 10 mV/s.

Mass spectrometric analysis

For all mass spectrometric measurements, a HPR-40 mass spectrometer from Hiden was used. Prior to any measurements, the mass spectrometer was pumped down to an idle pressure of $< 1.0 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar. During all measurements, constant voltages of 3 V and 90 V were applied to the cage and focus electrodes, respectively. If not specified otherwise, standard ionization conditions with 70 eV ionization energy and 500 μ A emission current were applied. For CO quantification, a reduced ionization energy of 16 eV and emission current of 100 μ A were used. The $m/z=28$ signal was amplified using a secondary electron multiplier detector, operated at a potential of 830 V, and analyzed using the Software MASsoft by Hiden. To prepare defined gas mixtures for the calibration measure-

ments, mass flow controllers red-y compact 2 series from Voegtlin were used in flow ranges between 5 and 200 sccm.

For headspace gas analysis, the instrument was equipped with a μ -flow capillary (gas consumption 12 μ L/min). During sampling, the total pressure inside the MS was found to be $3\text{--}6.0 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar, depending on the nature of the gas mixture and the absolute pressure at the sampling point. The CO measurement was performed by averaging over 10 datapoints measured within 7.5–8 min after injecting the capillary's cannula into the headspace of the electrochemical cell. Starting at 8 min after injection, all other gases of interest were analyzed under standard RGA conditions (ionization voltage of 70 V, emission current of 500 μ A and faraday cup detector, again averaging over 10 datapoints) using the QGA software by Hiden. Hydrogen, methane, ethylene, nitrogen, oxygen, argon and carbon dioxide were analyzed using the instrument's built-in software and procedures by their respective signals at $m/z = 2, 15, 27, 28, 32, 40$ and 44. To compensate for over- and under-pressure conditions occurring in the electrochemical cell after electrolysis analysis, heavily affecting the speed of gas displacement inside the capillary and total partial pressures inside the MS, a calibration procedure was developed to render the individual experiments comparable (see Supporting Information). The resulting correction factor was used for all product gases of interest.

Differential electrochemical mass spectrometry was performed with a Hiden DEMS direct probe inlet, featuring a nanoporous membrane for direct insertion into the aqueous electrolyte during electrolysis. During the measurement, the probe was placed approximately 3 mm above the working electrode at the bottom of the cell in order to maximize the capture of gas bubbles generated during electrolysis. The total pressure inside the MS during sampling was found to be 3 to 5×10^{-7} mbar.

Acknowledgements

This research is funded by the German Ministry of Education and Research: "ECO2nvert", grant No. 031B0870B. We thank Michael Bosch for Ag evaporation and Ivan Kundrata for Au sputter coating.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: carbon dioxide reduction · carbon monoxide quantification · differential electrochemical mass spectrometry · electrochemistry · mass spectrometry

- [1] a) G. A. Olah, G. K. Prakash, A. Goepfert, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 12881–12898; b) X. Li, P. Anderson, H.-R. M. Jhong, M. Paster, J. F. Stubbins, P. J. A. Kenis, *Energy Fuels* **2016**, *30*, 5980–5989; c) S. Jin, Z.

- Hao, K. Zhang, Z. Yan, J. Chen, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* **2021**, *60*, 20627–20648.
- [2] a) X. Wang, K. Klingan, M. Klingenhof, T. Moller, J. Ferreira de Araujo, I. Martens, A. Bagger, S. Jiang, J. Rossmeisl, H. Dau, P. Strasser, *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12*, 794; b) E. L. Clark, M. R. Singh, Y. Kwon, A. T. Bell, *Anal. Chem.* **2015**, *87*, 8013–8020; c) S. Nitopi, E. Bertheussen, S. B. Scott, X. Liu, A. K. Engstfeld, S. Horch, B. Seger, I. E. L. Stephens, K. Chan, C. Hahn, J. K. Nørskov, T. F. Jaramillo, I. Chorkendorff, *Chem. Rev.* **2019**, *119*, 7610–7672.
- [3] C. Thomas, G. Süß-Fink, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2003**, *243*, 125–142.
- [4] O. G. Sánchez, Y. Y. Birdja, M. Bulut, J. Vaes, T. Breugelmans, D. Pant, *Curr. Opin. Green Sustain. Chem.* **2019**, *16*, 47–56.
- [5] a) C. Kim, F. Dionigi, V. Beermann, X. Wang, T. Moller, P. Strasser, *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, e1805617; b) M. G. Kibriá, J. P. Edwards, C. M. Gabardo, C. T. Dinh, A. Seifitokaldani, D. Sinton, E. H. Sargent, *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, e1807166; c) A. Bagger, W. Ju, A. S. Varela, P. Strasser, J. Rossmeisl, *ChemPhysChem* **2017**, *18*, 3266–3273.
- [6] a) J. Hong, W. Zhang, J. Ren, R. Xu, *Anal. Methods* **2013**, *5*; b) T. Chatterjee, E. Boutin, M. Robert, *Dalton Trans.* **2020**, *49*, 4257–4265.
- [7] D. Sparkman, Z. Penton, F. Kitson, *Gas Chromatography and Mass Spectrometry: A Practical Guide*, 2nd ed., Academic Press, **2011**.
- [8] a) G.-C. Liu, X.-Y. Gong, Y. Jiang, Y.-Q. Piao, X. Fang, Z.-J. Huang, D. Tian, *Chinese Journal of Analytical Chemistry* **2019**, *47*, 686–694; b) C. J. Bondue, M. T. M. Koper, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **2020**, *875*.
- [9] a) J. M. Mora-Hernandez, W. I. González-Suárez, A. Manzo-Robledo, M. Luna-Trujillo, *J. CO₂ Util.* **2021**, *47*; b) A. C. Queiroz, M. L. Souza, M. R. Camilo, W. O. Silva, D. A. Cantane, I. Messias, M. R. Pinto, R. Nagao, F. H. B. Lima, *ChemElectroChem* **2022**, *9*, e202101408.
- [10] a) B. B. Berkes, A. Jozwiuk, H. Sommer, T. Brezesinski, J. Janek, *Electrochem. Commun.* **2015**, *60*, 64–69; b) M. Camilo, W. Silva, F. Lima, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.* **2017**.
- [11] a) R. Loch, M. Davister, *Int. J. Mass Spectrom. Ion Processes* **1995**, *144*, 105–129; b) A. N. Zaviropulo, F. F. Chipev, O. B. Shpenik, *Tech. Phys.* **2005**, *50*, 402–407.
- [12] W. E. W. NIST, *Mass Spectrometry Data Center, director, NIST Chemistry WebBook, NIST Standard Reference Database Number 69* (Ed.: E. P. J. L. a. W. G. Mallard), National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg MD, 20899, **2023**.
- [13] T.-W. Jiang, Y.-W. Zhou, X.-Y. Ma, X. Qin, H. Li, C. Ding, B. Jiang, K. Jiang, W.-B. Cai, *ACS Catal.* **2021**, *11*, 840–848.
- [14] E. L. Clark, A. T. Bell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2018**, *140*, 7012–7020.
- [15] a) Hiden-Analytical, *Gas Analysis Application Note 282*; http://www.hiden.de/wp-content/uploads/pdf/RS_Measurement_of_Gases_-_Hiden_Analytical_App_Note_282.pdf (accessed 22.03.2023); b) J. Otvos, D. Stevenson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1956**, *78*, 546–551; c) J. H. Leck, *Total and Partial Pressure Measurement in Vacuum Systems*, 1st ed., Springer New York, NY, **1989**.
- [16] a) H. S. Jeon, S. Kunze, F. Scholten, B. Roldan Cuenya, *ACS Catal.* **2017**, *8*, 531–535; b) F. S. Roberts, K. P. Kuhl, A. Nilsson, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* **2015**, *54*, 5179–5182.
- [17] a) D. V. Esposito, S. T. Hunt, A. L. Stottlemeyer, K. D. Dobson, B. E. McCandless, R. W. Birkmire, J. G. Chen, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* **2010**, *49*, 9859–9862; b) H. C. Kwon, M. Kim, J. P. Grote, S. J. Cho, M. W. Chung, H. Kim, D. H. Won, A. R. Zeradjanin, K. J. J. Mayrhofer, M. Choi, H. Kim, C. H. Choi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2018**, *140*, 16198–16205.
- [18] a) G. Marcandalli, M. C. O. Monteiro, A. Goyal, M. T. M. Koper, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2022**, *55*, 1900–1911; b) K. Ye, G. Zhang, X.-Y. Ma, C. Deng, X. Huang, C. Yuan, G. Meng, W.-B. Cai, K. Jiang, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2022**, *15*, 749–759; c) C. J. Bondue, M. Graf, A. Goyal, M. T. M. Koper, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2021**, *143*, 279–285.
- [19] N. Sahin, W. O. Silva, M. R. Camilo, E. A. Ticianelli, F. H. B. Lima, J. Parmentier, C. Comminges, T. W. Napporn, K. B. Kokoh, *Sustain. Energy Fuels* **2020**, *4*, 6045–6053.
- [20] a) N. Todoroki, H. Tei, H. Tsurumaki, T. Miyakawa, T. Inoue, T. Wadayama, *ACS Catal.* **2019**, *9*, 1383–1388; b) E. L. Clark, J. Resasco, A. Landers, J. Lin, L.-T. Chung, A. Walton, C. Hahn, T. F. Jaramillo, A. T. Bell, *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, 6560–6570.
- [21] F. D. Speck, S. Cherevko, *Electrochem. Commun.* **2020**, *115*, 106739.

Manuscript received: March 30, 2023

Version of record online: ■■■

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Careful adjustment of ionization energy enables the specific quantification of carbon monoxide in gas mixtures containing CO_2 and N_2 , both of which otherwise would cause interferences. This technique is applied for the analysis of CO_2 RR products, both for headspace gas analysis as well as in real-time analysis, also known as differential electrochemical mass spectrometry.

*J. Enghard, Prof. J. Bachmann**

1 – 7

Quantification of CO and Further CO_2 Reduction Products by On-line Mass Spectrometry

